

1 Integrals of life: tracking ecosystem spatial
2 heterogeneity from space through the area under
3 the curve of the parametric Rao's Q index

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February 27, 2023

Abstract

Spatio-ecological heterogeneity is strongly linked to many ecological processes and functions such as plant species diversity patterns and change, metapopulation dynamics, and gene flow. Remote sensing is particularly useful for measuring spatial heterogeneity of ecosystems over wide regions with repeated measurements in space and time. Besides, developing free and open source algorithms for ecological modelling from space is vital to allow to prove workflows of analysis reproducible. From this point of view, NASA developed programs like the Surface Biology and Geology (SBG) to support the development of algorithms for exploiting spaceborne remotely sensed data to provide a relatively fast but accurate estimate of ecological properties in vast areas over time. Most of the indices to measure heterogeneity from space are point descriptors : they catch only part of the whole heterogeneity spectrum. Under the SBG umbrella, in this paper we provide a new R function part of the `rasterdiv` R package which allows to calculate spatio-ecological heterogeneity and its variation over time by considering all its possible facets. The new function was tested on two different case studies, on multi- and hyperspectral images, proving to be an effective tool to measure heterogeneity and detect its changes over time.

Keywords— biodiversity, ecological informatics, modelling, remote sensing, satellite imagery

1 Introduction

The concept of spatiotemporal heterogeneity is crucial in ecological modelling to link spatial patterns to the generating processes and to the functional networking among organisms (Borcard et al., 1992). In ecological research, the search for new methods underlying spatiotemporal patterns in ecosystem heterogeneity has been a recurring theme (Rocchini and Ricotta, 2007; Atluri et al., 2018). Spatio-ecological hetero-

82 geneity, in this paper considered as the degree of non-uniformity in vegetation, land
83 cover, and physical factors (soil, topography, microclimate and topoclimate; (Stein et
84 al., 2014), has been proven to be strongly linked to many ecological processes and
85 functions such as plant species diversity patterns and change (Rocchini et al., 2018),
86 metapopulation dynamics (Fahrig, 2007), and gene flow (Lozier et al., 2013). Indeed,
87 an increase of spatial heterogeneity means an increase in the availability of ecological
88 niches, provision of refuges at relatively short distances and opportunities for spatial
89 isolation and local adaptation (Stein et al., 2014). As a consequence, species coexis-
90 tence, persistence and diversification are generally in strict relation with the degree of
91 environmental heterogeneity available within the landscape (Stein et al., 2014; Tews
92 et al., 2004). The development of new methods for measuring spatio-ecological het-
93 erogeneity is also fundamental to make estimations of its change in time in order to
94 improve conservation planning (Skidmore et al., 2021).

95 In this context, NASA developed programs like the Global Ecosystem Dynamics
96 Investigation (GEDI, <https://gedi.umd.edu/>) or the Surface Biology and Geology
97 (SBG) mission (<https://science.nasa.gov/earth-science/decadal-sbg>) exploit-
98 ing spaceborne remotely sensed data to provide a relatively fast but accurate estimate
99 of spatio-ecological heterogeneity in vast areas over time. In fact, spectral heterogene-
100 ity of an optical image - associated with the reflectance values of the pixels - can be
101 a proxy of the spatio-ecological heterogeneity (Rocchini, 2007). Hence, the variation
102 of spatio-ecological heterogeneity in space and time (e.g., phenological cycles) can be
103 effectively inferred using remote sensing (Schneider et al., 2017).

104 Therefore, the measure of ecosystem heterogeneity over time from satellite through
105 Free and Open Source Software and algorithms allows robust, reproducible and stan-
106 dardized estimates of ecosystem patterns and processes (Rocchini and Neteler, 2012).
107 Also, its use brings many advantages: availability, transparency and shareability. In
108 this context, the R platform is one of the most used statistical and computational
109 environment in ecology, partially thanks to the continuous development of relevant
110 packages. In particular, the `rasterdiv` package (Marcantonio et al. , 2021; Rocchini
111 et al., 2021; Thouverai et al., 2021) allows to calculate a plethora of different indices

112 to measure spatio-ecological heterogeneity from space.

113 Most of the algorithms have been related to Information Theory relying on abundance-
114 based metrics, starting from Shannon’s index (Shannon, 1949) (see section 2). How-
115 ever, some information about the spectral distance among pixel reflectance values
116 might be lost if not considered in the calculation (Rocchini et al., 2017). Currently,
117 the candidate for solving the problem is Rao’s Quadratic Entropy index (hereafter
118 Rao’s Q) (Rao, 1982): this index, besides the relative abundance of pixel values in
119 a given moving window or polygonal area, incorporates also their spectral distances
120 (section 2). Both Shannon and Rao’s Q indices are point descriptors of heterogene-
121 ity, namely they can only show part of the whole heterogeneity spectrum. Recently
122 Rocchini et al. (2021) proposed an implementation of the Rao’s Q index by param-
123 eterizing the original formula, and allowing the whole continuum of heterogeneity to
124 be measured thanks to Rao’s Q continuous profiles (see section 2).

125 This paper aims to show how to make proper use of the Rao’s continuum hetero-
126 geneity variation profile by proposing a new R function – integrated into the `rasterdiv`
127 R package (Marcantonio et al. , 2021) - which calculates AUC, the area under the
128 curve formed by applying the parametric Rao’s Q index (see section 2). Two case stud-
129 ies on multi- and hyperspectral satellite images are also provided in order to verify if
130 the new metric proposed could be an effective tool for the study of spatio-ecological
131 heterogeneity.

132 **2 The algorithm**

133 **2.1 The theory**

134 Algorithms that aim to measure environmental heterogeneity through remote sensing
135 data can rely on the moving window technique, which divides remotely sensed imagery
136 into user-defined squares (windows) to derive measures of heterogeneity. Examples are
137 included in the `rasterdiv` R package (Rocchini et al., 2021). One of the most used

138 metrics included in the package is the Shannon entropy index H (Shannon, 1949):

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \ln p_i \quad (1)$$

139 where the relative abundance of every pixel reflectance value calculated as the ratio
140 between the actual value of the pixel $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and the sum of the pixel values of
141 the moving window (p_i) in an image of N pixels is considered. It is usually calculated
142 of one layer images, such as a vegetation index or the first axis of a PCA. However,
143 Shannon's H does not consider the spectral distances among pixel reflectance values,
144 overestimating the heterogeneity of homogeneous surfaces (Rocchini et al., 2017). For
145 instance, when using Shannon's H , spectral values differing by a few decimals will
146 be treated the same as spectral values differing by several order of magnitudes. To
147 overcome this issue, Rao's Q index (Rao, 1982) can be used to include the pixel's
148 spectral distances in the calculation:

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N d_{ij} \times p_i \times p_j \quad (2)$$

149 where d_{ij} is the spectral distance between pixel i and pixel j and p_i and p_j are the
150 relative abundances of the pixels i and j in an assemblage of N pixels. The spectral
151 distance between pixels d_{ij} can be calculated over any number of layers and using any
152 metric for the calculation of pairwise distances. For example, in the `rasterdiv` pack-
153 age, the `Rao` function permits the calculation of Rao's Q choosing from "euclidean",
154 "manhattan", "canberra", "minkowski" and "mahalanobis" as the type of distance
155 calculated (Marcantonio et al., 2021). Both Shannon's H and Rao's Q are point de-
156 scriptors of heterogeneity, showing only one part of its potential spectrum. Therefore,
157 the use of generalized entropies, where one single formula represents a parameter-
158 ized version of an index, provides a continuum of heterogeneity metrics reflecting all
159 the characteristics of the heterogeneity spectrum. Rocchini et al. (2021) presented a
160 parametric version of Rao's Q allowing the characterisation of the dimensionality of

161 heterogeneity in different ecosystems:

$$Q_\alpha = \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^N \omega_{ij} d_{ij}^\alpha \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (3)$$

162 where d_{ij} is the spectral distance between pixel i and pixel j and ω_{ij} is the combined
163 probability ($1/N^2$) of extracting pixels i and j in this order in an image of N pixels.
164 In other words, parametric Rao's Q is a generalized mean that measures the expected
165 distance between two randomly chosen pixels regulated by the parameter α . The α
166 parameter provides a continuum of potential diversity indices by regulating the weight
167 of d_{ij} with the highest values obtaining different types of means as it is increasing
168 ($[\alpha \rightarrow 0] \Rightarrow$ geometric, $[\alpha = 1] \Rightarrow$ arithmetic, $[\alpha = 2] \Rightarrow$ quadratic, $[\alpha = 3] \Rightarrow$ cubic,
169 and so on till $[\alpha \rightarrow \infty] \Rightarrow \max_d$).

170 In this paper, we propose to calculate the area under the curve (AUC) constructed
171 by applying the index parametric Rao's Q over a sequence of α values. We want to
172 verify if AUC can be used to quantify the width of the diversity spectrum calculated
173 with parametric Q for each pixel, resulting in an image that can be exploited to monitor
174 the change in the heterogeneity spectrum over time for a selected area.

175 2.2 The R function

176 The function `rasterdiv::RaoAUC()` exploits the function `rasterdiv::paRao()` to de-
177 fine the values of the parametric Rao's Q using a vector of alphas decided by the user.
178 Accordingly, the values of parametric Rao's Q are calculated building a moving win-
179 dows around every pixel of the remote sensing image for every alpha selected. Then, the
180 integral of the curve formed by the values of the parametric Rao's Q index obtained
181 for every pixel is calculated.

182 3 Examples

183 In this section, we present one theoretical examples and two case studies for the new R
184 function proposed (`RaoAUC()`). Specifically, AUC was calculated for one layer, multi-

185 and hyperspectral satellite images of areas afflicted by a sudden event that changed the
186 spatio-ecological heterogeneity of the area. We choose two images per case study of two
187 different moments in time and calculated the difference between the two, highlighting
188 the increase in heterogeneity.

189 **3.1 A theoretical example**

190 In this section, we will show how to use the function `accRao()` from the `rasterdiv`
191 package to calculate the accumulation function (integral) of Rao values obtained using
192 a range of alpha-values. We used a raster for the global average NDVI rescaled at 8-bit
193 available from `rasterdiv`. This raster was first cropped on the islands of Sardinia and
194 Corsica. In order to simulate the effects of an ecological perturbation, for example
195 widespread drought, we created a new raster with perturbed NDVI values for these
196 two islands. Pixels with NDVI higher than 150 were decreased using values from a
197 normal distribution centered on 50 with a standard deviation of 5. Then, we applied
198 `accRao()` both on the original and simulated raster by using alphas ranging from 1 to
199 10:

```

RaoAUC.before ← accRao(
  alphas = 1:10, #range of alphas

  x = ndvi.before, #raster layer

  dist_m = "euclidean", #method for the
                        #calculation of the
                        #spectral distance

  window = 3, #dimension of the moving window

  method = "classic", #specifies if the function
                     #is applied on a single
                     #layer or on a
                     #multidimensional system

  rasterAUC = TRUE, #specifies if the output
                   #will be a raster layer or
                   #a matrix

  na.tolerance = 0.4, #proportion of NA values
                    #tolerated

  np = 1 #number of cores which will be spawned
)

RaoAUC.after ← accRao(alphas=1:10,
  x = ndvi.after,
  dist_m = "euclidean",
  window = 3,
  method = "classic", 10
  rasterAUC=TRUE,
  na.tolerance=0.4, np=1)

```

201 Afterwards, the difference between the two rasters, before and after the simulated
202 perturbation, was calculated (Figure 1). Also, the average parametric Rao of the
203 images in Figure 1 was calculated for every α value, and the resulting curves are
204 showed in Figure 2.

205 **accRao()** function derives the value of parametric Rao for each pixel using a moving
206 window algorithm. To illustrate how this methodology works, we applied **paRao()** on
207 a single group of neighbor pixels, which represents a moving window, from the two
208 NDVI rasters and with alphas ranging from 1 to 10 as follows:

```

#Selection of the 3x3 window
ndvi.pix.b ← ndvi.before[41:43,
  21:23,drop = FALSE]
ndvi.pix.a ← ndvi.after[41:43, 21:23,drop=FALSE]

#Set the alpha interval
alphas ← 1:10

#Set the number of pixels in the selected window
N ← 3^2

#Function to calculate paRao over the set alphas
RaoFx ← function(alpha,N,D) {
  ( sum((1/(N^4)) * D^alpha )*2)^(1/alpha)
}

#Calculation of paRao before
rao.b ← sapply(alphas, function(a) {
  RaoFx(alpha = a, N = N,
  D = as.vector(ndvi.pix.b))})

#Calculation of paRao after
rao.a ← sapply(alphas, function(a) {
  RaoFx(alpha = a, N = N,
  D = as.vector(ndvi.pix.a))})

```

209

210 From the values obtained (a parametric value for each alpha), the area under the

211 curve was calculated integrating the results (Figure 3):

```

#Calculation of AUC before
RaoAUC.bf ← approxfun(x = alphas, y = rao.b)
RaoAUC.b ← integrate(RaoAUC.bf, lower = 1,
  upper = 10, subdivisions = 500)

#Calculation of AUC after
RaoAUC.af ← approxfun(x = alphas, y = rao.a)
RaoAUC.a ← integrate(RaoAUC.af, lower = 1,
  upper = 10, subdivisions = 500)

```

212

213 3.2 Empirical examples

214 In this section, the `accRao()` function is tested on two real-world case studies by
 215 comparing remotely sensed images before and after a perturbation event. AUC is
 216 calculated on multi- and hyperspectral images, exploiting the information that every
 217 band holds to estimate the spatio-ecological heterogeneity.

218 3.2.1 Example 1: Fire spread in the Kangaroo island (Australia)

219 This section focuses on the major fire-affected area of Kangaroo Island in January
 220 2020, in particular on Flinders Chase NP and the associated Ravine Des Casoars
 221 Wilderness Protection Area. Two cloudless images from Copernicus Sentinel-2 (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>) with a spatial resolution of 10m before (January 2019) and
 222 after (January 2021) were compared (Figure 4). The `accRao()` function was applied on
 223 the 2 multispectral images (Red, Green, Blue and NIR bands) using a moving window
 224 of 9×9 pixels and the parameter alpha was set to a range of 1 to 5:
 225

```

#accRao() function
accRao(alphas = 1:5, x = kanga_multi,
       dist_m = "euclidean", window = 9,
       method = "multidimension", rasterAUC = TRUE,
       na.tolerance = 0.9, np = 1)

```

226

227 Subsequently, the difference between the obtained AUC images was calculated,
 228 with positive values meaning an increase in spatio-ecological heterogeneity (Figure
 229 4). In this case, the AUC of Rao's Q profiles succeeded to highlight areas where
 230 the perturbation (fire) event caused an increase of spatial heterogeneity of vegetation
 231 which was more homogeneous (continuous woodland cover) before the perturbation.

232 3.2.2 Example 2: Post fire in Santa Barbara, California

233 For the last empirical examples two hyperspectral images of a postfire scene in Santa
 234 Barbara (California) were downloaded from AVIRIS <https://aviris.jpl.nasa.gov/>
 235 platform. The first image is from June 2009, the second from June 2011 in order to
 236 visualize the recovery of the vegetation after the fire event (see Figure 5). The `accRao()`
 237 function was applied over all the 224 bands of the two images using a moving window
 238 of 9×9 pixels and setting the α parameter to a range of one to 5:

```

#accRao() function
accRao(alphas = 1:5, x = santabarbara_hyper,
       dist_m = "euclidean", window = 9,
       method = "multidimension", rasterAUC = TRUE,
       na.tolerance = 0.9, np = 1)

```

239

240 Subsequently, the difference between the obtained AUC images was calculated as in

241 the previous examples (Figure 6). The difference between the obtained AUC highlights
242 subtle changes of spatio-ecological heterogeneity in the studied area between 2009 and
243 2011.

244 4 Discussion

245 The study of landscape structure has been steadily growing in recent years (e.g.,
246 Lichstein et al., 2002; Saravia, 2015) with the development of several methodologies
247 and approaches, which have been tested ecosystems and supported in the scientific
248 literature (see Bar-Massada and Wood, 2014). In particular, the use and availability of
249 remote sensing data have made it possible to assess specific heterogeneity patterns over
250 various ecosystems, with increasing performance in terms of spectral/spatial/temporal
251 characteristics, opening up new possibilities for exploring complex ecological processes.

252 Using our algorithm, environmental heterogeneity is estimated by the range of
253 spectral values associated to the spatial variability within a given habitat. Hence,
254 environmental heterogeneity can be evaluated contiguously, from regional to conti-
255 nental extents, according to the remote sensing data used and the spatial extent of
256 the analysis. Among the heterogeneity metrics, parametric Rao's Q adds a layer of
257 information to classical estimates of heterogeneity from remotely sensed multispectral
258 data. This index considers pairwise pixel spectral distance to separate areas with high
259 richness but low evenness from those with low richness but high evenness (Rocchini et
260 al., 2017).

261 In addition, the parametric Rao's Q can be calculated in a multivariate system
262 such as a multi-temporal system, i.e. long time series, in order to improve the as-
263 sessments and prediction of changes in spatio-ecological heterogeneity over space and
264 time (Rugani and Rocchini, 2016). Also, by considering multiple bands, it has a
265 higher capability to discern subtle diversity changes over the landscape (Torresani et
266 al., 2019).

267 In this paper, all the potential facets of heterogeneity were investigated by param-
268 eterizing the Rao's Q metric and calculating the area under the curve of continuous

269 entropy profiles. This would be particularly useful when dealing with multitemporal
270 sets, with increases or decreases of heterogeneity provoked by different ecological pro-
271 cesses like drought (subsection 3.1, see also Jiao et al., 2020) and fire (subsection 3.2.1,
272 see also Chuvieco and Kasischke, 2007; subsection 3.2.2).

273 The application of AUC on Rao's Q in before / after ecological perturbation sce-
274 narios can help pointing out areas with the highest difference in spectral heterogeneity,
275 by considering the whole heterogeneity continuum. For example, subsection 3.2.2 of
276 two postfire scenes shows the sensibility of the algorithm in highlight even subtle land-
277 scape changes using multiple bands for the analysis. Heterogeneity of ecosystems is
278 multifaceted in its very nature. As stressed by (Gorelick, 2011) there is no "true het-
279 erogeneity" measurement since important holistic aspects of ecosystems are inevitably
280 lost once making use of single metrics. From this point of view, the proposed general-
281 ized entropy, based on a parameterization of the Rao's Q entropy (and its area under
282 the curve) can help catching the multidimensionality of ecosystem heterogeneity com-
283 ponents (Nakamura et al., 2020), avoiding the intrinsic fallacy of a single best index
284 of true heterogeneity (Gorelick, 2011).

285 Moreover, the Rao's Q original formula directly takes into account the distance
286 among values (pixel reflectances once applied to remote sensing imagery). This leads to
287 the possibility of accounting for the turnover among reflectances, also known as beta-
288 diversity in ecology (Rocchini et al., 2018). Since little consensus has been reached as
289 to general measures of heterogeneity / beta-diversity measurement in literature (Koleff
290 et al., 2003), the aforementioned use of a generalized metric like the parametric Rao's
291 Q helps detecting gradients in reflectance beta-diversity change (turnover) over space,
292 otherwise hidden when relying on point descriptors of heterogeneity, i.e. single metrics
293 like the commonly used Shannon and Simpson indices in remote sensing applications
294 (Nagendra, 2002). In other words, while a wide range of approaches has been used to
295 catch the variation of ecosystem properties, finding ways to generalize heterogeneity
296 measurement could represent a consistent approach to describe heterogeneity patterns
297 change in space and time (Haralick & Kelly , 1969).

298 The use of a continuum of diversities as in the parametric Rao's Q leads to the

299 understanding of hidden parts of the whole diversity of dimensionalities (Nakamura
300 et al., 2020). Increasing alpha in Equation 3 will increase the weight of higher dis-
301 tances among different values until reaching the maximum distance value possible
302 (Rocchini et al., 2021). For this reason, spatio-ecological heterogeneity values of the
303 parametric Rao's Q increase with each alpha progressively added to the calculation
304 constructing a curve for every moving window built around each pixel (Rocchini et
305 al., 2021). Consequently, applying an integral, it is possible to calculate the area un-
306 der every pixel's window area curve obtaining a new spatio-ecological heterogeneity
307 metric, AUC. Hence, the `accRao()` function can highlight the differences before and
308 after an ecological perturbation both in the theoretical and in the empirical examples
309 (Figures 1, 4 and 6) showing the change in the whole heterogeneity continuum and
310 being able to detect both: (i) spatially wide heterogeneity change patterns, as in the
311 Kangaroo Island's fires example (see subsection 3.2.1), as well as (ii) spatially local-
312 ized differences in space and time, as in the post fire in Santa Barbara example (see
313 subsection 3.2.2).

314 The three examples proposed in section 3, show the application of AUC on one
315 layer (subsection 3.1), multispectral (subsection 3.2.1) and hyperspectral 3.2.2 satellite
316 images. However, for the hyperspectral images it is difficult to address a cause for the
317 heterogeneity change: because of the high number of bands exploited for the analysis
318 we can't know which ones weight more in the measure of the index. Analysis like the
319 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or correlation matrices can help to highlight
320 the bands which give more contribution in the calculation of the spatio-ecological
321 heterogeneity.

322 Also, in the empirical case studies only a range of alpha between 1 and 5 was tested
323 because of the high computational complexity of the function `accRao()` as it is now.
324 We are actually working to speed up the algorithm, so it would be interesting in a
325 future study to test different ranges of alpha. In this context, it would also be helpful
326 the study of the influence of the number of bands and their resolution on the measure
327 of AUC, as highlighted by the Santa Barbara subsection (see subsection 3.2.2).

328 In conclusion, the integration over an alpha range is more convenient than having

329 to choose a single alpha level as the most representative level of diversity. This task
330 is often complicated as there is no direct interpretation for the meaning of indexes
331 calculated with different alphas. Here, we propose the way forward to re-conciliate
332 the advantage of having a single metrics without the need of choosing a single alpha
333 value.

334 5 Conclusion

335 In this paper, we provided a practical demonstration of the effectiveness of a method
336 that can supply measures of generalized entropy at different spatial scales and in
337 different contexts. Generalized means represent an effective tool to develop a uni-
338 fying notation for a large family of parametric diversity and dissimilarity functions
339 (Ricotta et al., 2021). Indeed, binding different heterogeneity metrics in order to
340 analyze ecosystem changes proved to be a reliable approach to enhance the output
341 information. Although remote sensing data have long held the promise of transform-
342 ing environmental monitoring efforts, publicly accessible tools leveraging these data
343 to achieve actionable in-sights have been lacking. We suggest that Rao's AUC can
344 be useful to identify areas more vulnerable to environmental changes , and to develop
345 and implement appropriate habitat management plans and environmental policies.

346 6 Acknowledgements

347 This study has received funding from the project SHOWCASE (SHOW - CASingsyn-
348 ergies between agriculture, biodiversity and ecosystems ser- vices to help farmers capi-
349 talising on native biodiversity) within the European Union's Horizon 2020 Researcher
350 and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 862480. DR was also supported
351 by the Horizon Europe project Earthbridge.

352 PZ was supported by LifeWatch Italy through the project LifeWatch- PLUS (CIR01.00028).

353 RF is supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation, Switzer- land SNSF175529.

354 ETo is supported by the Estonian Research Council, grant code MOBJD1030.

355 MM is supported by the FRS-FNRS and by the “Action de Recherche concertée”
356 grant number 17/22-086.

357 DR, MM, MG and ET contributed to the development of the R function and to
358 the analysis. DR, PZ and ET contributed to the implementation of the figures. All
359 the authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

360 The rasterdiv package that contains the new function proposed can be downloaded
361 at <https://github.com/mattmar/rasterdiv> or directly from the CRAN ([https://](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv)
362 CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv). The hyperspectral images of Santa Bar-
363 bara of June 2009 and 2011 can be respectively retrieved from [https://popo.jpl.](https://popo.jpl.nasa.gov/avcl/y09_data/f090826t01p00r08.tar.gz)
364 [nasa.gov/avcl/y09_data/f090826t01p00r08.tar.gz](https://popo.jpl.nasa.gov/avcl/y09_data/f090826t01p00r08.tar.gz) and [https://popo.jpl.nasa.](https://popo.jpl.nasa.gov/avcl/y11_data/f110719t01p00r19.tar.gz)
365 [gov/avcl/y11_data/f110719t01p00r19.tar.gz](https://popo.jpl.nasa.gov/avcl/y11_data/f110719t01p00r19.tar.gz). The images of Kangaroo Island can
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Figure 1: From left to right: the NDVI images of Sardinia and Corsica before and after the simulated perturbation, the correspondent AUC images and their difference after - before the simulated perturbation.

Figure 2: Three curves representing respectively: the mean values of parametric Rao's Q (i) before (yellow) and (ii) after (grey) the simulated ecological perturbation (drought) of Figure 1, their correspondent confidence intervals and (iii) their difference (after - before, dashed line) over increasing alphas.

Figure 3: Curves representing the values of parametric Rao's Q for one pixel before (yellow) and after (grey) the simulated ecological perturbation (drought) of Figure 1 over increasing alphas. The area under the curve (AUC) is highlighted.

Figure 4: On top left, the Kangaroo Island before and after the fires (the area used for the analysis is highlighted) and the selected area before and after the fire in RGB false color (NIR, red, green); on the right the correspondent AUC images and their difference after - before the fire.

Santa Barbara RGB

Figure 5: Post fire in Santa Barbara 2009 (left) and 2011 (right). The area within the square is the studied area.

Figure 6: From the top: RGB images of the study area (Santa Barbara, CA) in 2009 and 2011, the correspondent AUC images and their difference 2011 - 2009.